

Insights on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Tourism & Hospitality Industry: A View Point

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of the present article is to analyze the use and role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the tourism and hospitality industry. In the recent time, especially amid and post covid-19, various latest technologies are being integrated to safeguarding the guest/travelers from the infections and improving the experience and services.

Design/methodology/approach: Authors are tried to find out the influence of technological advancements especially, the use of AI through systematic study on the reference of studies conducted in the last decade and presented in the form of view point.

Findings: AI certainly enhances tourism experiential services, safeguarding the guest from infections, however the affordability and dependency on such technology is still a matter of concern. Furthermore, such technology cannot surpass the human touch which is an essential determinant of experiential tourism & hospitality services. AI is acting as an effective and complementary dimension to the future of tourism and hospitality industry. With the emergence use of artificial intelligence, it is simpler to make travel arrangements by customers and businesses to know about the travel motives, interest of inclination, preferences etc.

Managerial and practical implications: Hospitality and Tourism marketing to see a positive and improved change that will develop the guest's/tourists' overall experience due to the use of AI and Robotics.

Furthermore, latest emerging technologies like robots, virtual reality, chatbots, language translators etc. can be effectively applied in Tourism and hospitality industry.

Research Approach: Conceptual and review with viewpoint

Keywords: Tourism and Hospitality Industry, Technological Innovations, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Internet of things

INTRODUCTION

In the recent times, technology and innovations has defined many goals and objectives of the industries in terms of their sustainability and business strategies. In this technological era, artificial intelligence has emerged as one of the most innovative tool that has transformed many industries tremendously around the globe (Russel Norvig 2016, P.4). As per definitions by John McCarthy (2004), the father of artificial intelligence (AI) “It is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs. While, As per Stuart Russell & peter Norvig, AI has four potential goals or definitions on the basis of rationality, thinking v/s acting, human approach and ideal approach. Further, AI can be classified in to two categories i.e. weak AI and strong AI. Weak AI is also referred as narrow AI or Artificial Narrow Intelligencce (ANI). This AI is trained and focused on to perform specific task. It enables some very robust applications like Apple’s Siri, Amazon’s Alexa, IBM Watson and autonomous vehicles etc. whereas strong AI is made up of Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) and Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI), it is theoretical form of AI, where machine would have intelligence equaled to human, these could have ability to learn, self awareness or consciousness, solve problems and plan for the future. ASI is also known as Super intelligence, would surpass the ability and intelligence of human brain (IBM, 2021). In the recent decade AI is being used in various forms like facial recognition, character recognition and many other heuristic searches. By the year 1980s considerable progress has been seen especially in the technological driven fields such as manufacturing, healthcare, financial services, banking, automobile, telecommunication, energy and other allied industries with travel, tourism & hospitality industry and even its application has increased significantly (Issa et al., 2016). Promptly, the use of AI is expanding in all sorts of industries all across the globe with every passing day (sites.tcs.com, 2019, p. 6). In the last couple of years AI has made its

solid presence in the hospitality and tourism industry due to restrictions of government regulations for preventing the infections of the Covid-19 diseases. Amid and post pandemic major brands of the tourism and hospitality has begun to install AI voice assistants like Alexa, Amazon Echo in their updated smart rooms. Similarly many companies are robustly using chatboats and evolving search & booking database, virtual reality tours etc. to protect and attract their customers and taking the advantage of AI and machine learning thereof (ehotelier, 2021). Further, this paper envisages the viewpoint on use of AI in the tourism and hospitality industry in detail.

HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WITH KEY DATES AND NAMES

As per some sources, the idea of 'a machine that thinks' dates back to ancient Greece. However, since the beginning of electronic computing some of the major events and milestones in the evolution of artificial intelligence may include following mentioned in the below table.

Table 1: Historical background of Artificial Intelligence, Source: IBM

Year	Major milestone in the field of Artificial Intelligence
1950	Alan Turing publishes Computing Machinery and Intelligence. In the paper, Turing—famous for breaking the Nazi's ENIGMA code during WWII—proposes to answer the question 'can machines think?' and introduces the Turing Test to determine if a computer can demonstrate the same intelligence (or the results of the same intelligence) as a human. The value of the Turing test has been debated ever since.
1956	John McCarthy coins the term 'artificial intelligence' at the first-ever AI conference at Dartmouth College. Later that year, Allen Newell, J.C. Shaw, and Herbert Simon create the Logic Theorist, the first-ever running AI software program.
1967	Frank Rosenblatt builds the Mark 1 Perceptron, the first computer based on a neural network that 'learned' through trial and error. Just a year later, Marvin Minsky and Seymour Papert publish a book titled 'Perceptrons', which becomes both the landmark work on neural networks and, at least for a while, an argument against future neural network research projects
1980s	Neural networks which use a back propagation algorithm to train, it become widely used in AI applications.
1997	IBM's Deep Blue beats then world chess champion Garry Kasparov, in a chess match (and rematch).
2011	IBM Watson beats champions Ken Jennings and Brad Rutter at Jeopardy

2015	Baidu's Minwa supercomputer uses a special kind of deep neural network called as a convolutional neural network, use to identify and categorize images with a higher rate of accuracy than the average human
2016	Deep Mind's Alpha Go program, powered by a deep neural network, beats Lee Sodol, the world champion Go player, in a five-game match. The victory is significant given the huge number of possible moves as the game progresses (over 14.5 trillion after just four moves). Later, Google purchased Deep Mind for a reported \$400 million.

TOURISM AND HOTEL INDUSTRY & ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Indian hotel industry has a vast history, it developed through the age's right from British era to present or contemporary or modern era. The present hotels are technological driven, where most of the works are done through technology rather manually. It is also predicted that the hotel of the future will be a "green hotel" or an "eco-hotel" where energy conservation and preservation of ecosystem shall be the prime need. However, by the advancement of the technology, there is the choice of the location, equipment, construction, hotel products and hotel services etc. (Ivanka, 2003). The applications of artificial intelligence can be recognized with various functions and tasks performed by the machines that operates with robotic technology. Many literatures define this technology with RAISA (Robotics, Artificial Intelligence and Service Automation). RAISA provides ample of opportunities to improve productivity, operations and simultaneously to improve consistent quality (Ivanov, Westeler & Berezina, 2017). In the Hospitality and Tourism industry, applications of AI are more over to substitution of human labour. Botha & Van Rensberg, 2010; Gentile Spiller & Noci, 2017; Verhof et al, 2017; Klaus & Maklan, 2013, focuses that management of customer experience, operations and process etc. are the key for loyal customers and then loyal customer to hotel advocates. The formation of guest's satisfied experience is complex process. It includes customer's over all experience i.e. pre, during and after stay at hotel. Similar case is with the tourism product service. AI has its many folds as per the industries desire and usage; however, some of the major interest of the hospitality and tourism industry may be recognized as below:

Table: 2.1, various types of AI application used in the Tourism & Hospitality Industry, Source: Authors, compiled from literatures

AI application used in the Tourism & Hospitality Industry
Ambient Intelligence
As per the article by Aarts Wichert, 2009, P.244 & J. Bulchand-Gidumal,2020, P.6, Aml is sensitive, adaptive and electronic environment which responds as per the action of person or object and cater accordingly. For example, smart room may adapt its temperature, light and music etc. as per the desire of a person or guest in the room. Moreover it is not just suitable for hotel room but can be used for public places such as airport lounge or concert hall.
NLP & Facial Recognition
Natural Language Processing enable computer to process language properly. Nowadays NLP is one of the most required elements in the automatic transportation. In tourism, importance of NLP is very high, as it enables virtual travel assistants, robots and other conventional systems (Tussyadiah & Miller, 2019). Whereas, face recognition is usually require to identify person in digital image or in a video. A very frequent example can be seen during check-in process at airport or hotel front desk. Face recognition technique enable to count number of people at certain area as well as knowing emotions by facial expressions. During the Covid-19, such techniques were used to identify the unmasked people in the crowd or at certain place.
Machine Learning, Deep Learning & Neural Network
Machine Learning, Deep Learning are both the part of Artificial Intelligence, machine learning is a set of algorithm by which machine learn, process and provides output after performing processes. However such task is conducted on very large data set. Example: machine may choose the best picture out of traveler’s memory. Whereas deep learning is based on neural network, where small set of information/instruction on how to modify a model to make it more accurate and stronger (Bulchand-Gidumal, 2016). Both the process and techniques in tourism are used in weather prediction, sentimental analysis, fraud prevention and video & image recognition etc. Neural network is group of techniques that can be used for deep learning and machine learning both, through the use of neural network. AI tries to imitate human neuron and their connection through ANN (Artificial Neural Network). These neurons are connected to similar way as human neurons are connected. The main use of the neural network in the tourism and hospitality is the forecasting (Claveria et al. 2015 & J. Bulchand-Gidumal, 2020)

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SYSTEMS

AI provides number of systems for the global industries in terms of applications and usage, however Tourism and Hospitality recognizes some of the major systems as below, which are helping in marketing, operations, travel experiences, inventory management etc. and proving them advantageous over to conventional modus of operandi.

- **Recommender and Personalization System:** It has been a general approach of the tourists to decide the destination by virtue of their budget, picture of catalogue or advertisement over the media or the offerings by the travel agent. AI changes this behavior by finding the alternatives that suits best, simultaneously business also cater the need as per the desire or specifications by traveler. Recommender and personalization technique try to provide the customized set of information based upon the preferences and restriction of the customer (Gao et al., 2010).
- **Forecasting Systems:** In Tourism and Hospitality forecasting can be used to understand the tourist's need or demand (Buhalis & Leung, 2018), enables to develop financial management, human resource requirement & allocation and marketing strategies. However, it requires big data and sometimes results are mixed in nature.
- **Language Translation Application System:** As per Cohen (2014), tourism process involve the travelers from different languages and sometimes language becomes the barrier which the tourists occasionally face and becomes hindrance in the experiencing of local culture. AI's personalization system helps tourist in automatic translation for navigating the destination, and allows experiencing and exploring all types of activities.
- **Conversational Systems:** conversational systems such as chatbots and voice assistant allow customer to engage in conversation which is generally required for information search (Gretzel, 2011). These systems involve technology such as NLP & speech recognition. Some of the common examples are Amazon-Alexa, Apple-Siri, Google-Assistant, and Microsoft Cortana etc. and are used through smart mobile phones, tablets and home speakers.

OBJECTIVES OF RESEARCH PAPER

The study will focus on understanding the various concepts, evolutions of artificial intelligence with the below key objectives.

1. To understand the modern day artificial intelligence with its applications in the Tourism and Hospitality.

2. To understand the acceptability of artificial intelligence in the Tourism and Hospitality industry.
3. To generate a view point over the impact of artificial intelligence in the Hospitality and Tourism industry with various challenges by reviewing and referring the literature.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article utilized conceptual approach with generating a view point on the topic. As the topic is new and latest in the field of hospitality, the use of artificial intelligence has gained a momentum especially during the pandemic covid-19. Soon after the restrictions over the hotel and tourism sector, hoteliers tried to find solution to bounce back through the use of technology and innovation to protect the guest and their employees. Author's search included the pertinent new articles and reports, however to develop the concept over evolution, definition, older articles have also taken in consideration. The major search was the high index peer reviewed article from the Scopus and web of science data base. Articles were accessed through Google scholar by the keyword search.

DISCUSSIONS

As per the study by Lei Peng (2020), Scholars have focused on two aspects of the AI in the hospitality industry. The first one is the use of AI in the Hospitality industry project analysis which is highlighted by Sun Lei (2019), Ulrike Gretezel (2020), Zhang Jinqui (2019) and Ziang Zhang (2020) that AI is being used in front desk check-in check-out, intelligent room lead, smart room product experience etc. mainly through face recognition, mobile payment, room preference, virtual portraits and human computer interaction etc., which optimize the customer accommodation experience. Whereas second one is emphasized on hotel to precision marketing that helps in improving the hotel business performances. Although, it poses challenges for maintaining of hardware facilities and database storage. Further, Li Guying and Xie Dingmcc (2020) and Feng Chaosheng (2019) stressed that AI application for hotel and tourism is double edged sword, where must see its negative impacts over to positive as well. These may be high operating cost, less humanized services and changes in employee's working styles. In the table 1&2.1, we have discussed various types of the AI systems and their applications in Tourism and Hospitality industry. However, I will be imperative if author discuss the specific

devices and integrated systems that are visibly seen in the hotel and tourism operations in the last few years. Some of the prominent are:

- **Mobile Applications:** Mobile applications (smart phone & tablet) allows customer to find best suitable hotel as per their need. Customer examine information like room type, facilities of SPA and health, auxiliary services etc. many hotel companies offer their own APPs while OTA offers wide range of hotel products.
- **Virtual reality:** It is the latest technology that creates non physical reality through information and communication systems (Gutierrez et al., 2008, Mc Neal & New Year, 2013).
- **Chatbots:** Chatbots are also called virtual agents, artificial conversational entities, instant messaging bots etc. these are computer programs that can respond to text questions, verbal commands and provides advice in place of human employee.
- **Robots:** Traditionally robots were found in the industrial or line set up but in the last few years, AI has allowed robots to appear in the service sector as well (Inavoc & Webster, 2017), the service of the robots has helped in fulfilling the shortfall of human resources in tourism and hospitality sector mainly for language barrier and labor shortage (Bowen & Morosen, 2018), particularly many chain hotels are using robots during the infection of COvid-19. Inavoc & Webster, (2017), mentioned two types of service robots i.e. personal service and professional service robots. As per Li et al. (2019), AI enabled service robots are abundantly being used to streamline process and doing task better than traditionally performed by front office and other service staff.
- **Smart Travel Assistant:** These AI powered virtual assistant can perform various task related with travel, they are also coupled with Internet of Things (IoT) and factor in both areas information (outside and internal) helps in flight schedule, country events, hotel availability, traffic condition, weather etc. (Chatterjee, A. & Shivakantamneni, 2017). These systems are also called intelligent travel agents, smart concierge or autonomous agents (J. Bulchand –Gidumal, 2020).
- **Smart Tourism and Smart Destination:** As per J. Bulchand-Gidumal, (2020), smart tourism and smart destinations are the digital ecosystem in which artificial Intelligence plays a vital

role. Such tourism may be defined as form of tourism, that is supported by integrated efforts at destination to collect and harness the data derived from social conventions, government bodies, physical infrastructure and human bodies in combination with use of advanced technology to transform that data in to business value proposition & on site experience with focus on sustainability, efficiency and experience enrichment (Gretzel et al., 2015).

Along with the above, mobile applications, IVR, Virtual reality, digital concierge, touch-less entry points, keyless entry doors, robotic services etc. have seen predominantly in the last couple of years.

Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Tourism and Hospitality

As hospitality and tourism industry is one of the main industry that have its major impact on the global GDP. After deliberately analyzing the impact of AI on hospitality and tourism in detailed manner as described above also, AI is mainly implemented in four areas i.e. Operational Management, Human Resource Management, Financial Management and Marketing Management.

Figure 1: Impact of AI & Service Automation in Tourism & Hospitality, Source: Ivanov, S. & Webster, C., (2019)

AI has been adopted a key member of the operations by many international chain hotels and tourism enterprises, its functions has been seen in the figure: 1, further, in the hotel industry, the below mentioned model, shows the shift of automation and applications of AI and robotic, which makes the hotel cost effective as well. Whereas, in augmented approach of hotel, where human perform the functions in combination with robots and AI automations. While distinguished hotel are fully operates on the human resources.

Figure 2, Hotel Operations with applications of AI, Robotics and automation, Source: Illustrations by author through literatures.

RECENT TRENDS OF AI AUTOMATION AND ROBOTICS

Particularly amid and post covid-19, scholars are intensifying their knowledge towards artificial intelligence and robotic automation and tried to augmented the literature in the field (Dwidi et al., 2021); Huang & Rust, 2020, though during the infections, hoteliers also in hurried to adopt the automation and robotics in to their business and gradually started to provide front line service to their guest (Belanche et al., 2020). Moreover, significance of cleanliness, hygiene, sanitation, social distancing, follow up of medical guidelines etc. was significantly increased. Considering the situation hotel brands like Marriot, Hilton, Hyatt etc. have already adopted technology for maintaining the social distancing and protecting guest and their employees from infections. Hotel brought the modifications in their SOPs and upgraded disinfection systems like electrostatic sprayers & UV technology (Sharma et al., 2021). Apart with many traditional and routine works such as meetings, conferences, health hygiene, cleaning, wellness etc. turned in to

technologically augmented mode. Below figure: 3; depicts the impact of AI and automation in the operations of the hotel and hotelier after covid-19, where majority of work were being done at home such as work from home, conferences through AI enabled platforms, virtual meeting, virtual events, health and hygiene were also part of consideration, simulation trainings, cloud kitchen operations in the food production department, mobile enabled or APPs enabled servicing of food and beverages etc. Furthermore, The increasing health and wellbeing trend will provide many opportunities to the hotel business to attract guests by promoting extremely relaxing and wellness centered programs like, preventive healthcare, balanced diet, modified nutrition and health products, spa etc. using AI enabled devices.

Figure 3,, Hotel Operations with applications of AI, Robotics and automation at Home as a Hotel Model, Source: Author's self Illustrations

ISSUES AND CHALLENGES FOR AI ADOPTION

However, we are required to see the other side of the coin as well. Over to the challenges and issues of adopting AI and technology, Reddy, (2006), state that artificial intelligence is excelling rapidly, however, there is still a limitation of its usage by illiterates. Even though, AI is providing unique experiences to the customer but it is still cannot surpass the human intelligence, it is still an emerging area (Laurent et al., 2015). Other major challenge for the adopting AI systems in the business is the safety and security of data. Chatbots and other similar AI devices store the purchase history, travel history, which posses challenge for the data privacy and security issue (Kannan &

Bernoff, 2019). Further, the software of these systems may be attacked by malwares, which can disrupt the software, programs and operations conducted by small service providers, which may lead to chaos. Despite the fact that AI is advanced and forward looking, but cannot be afford by small service providers as it requires huge investment (Morphy et al., 2017). Although, robots and chatbots are able to replace the human resource but customer still rely on human workforce, especially in terms of complex situations (Lommatzsch, 2018).

CONCLUSION

In the last few years, due to emergence of innovative technology, tourism industry will certainly reach the unimaginable heights in the coming years. As per recent research study, the artificial intelligence is expected to grow by 9% during the period of 2010-2023 and according an article by Forbes India, many jobs will be created because the rise in AI. In the last two years, when the entire world was struggling and fighting with Covid-19 pandemic, AI enabled devices helped to create an array of hope and to some extent, it has been successful also. Now the AI adoption rate by the industry is increasing day by day. The application of artificial intelligence in tourism and hospitality provides wide variety of self services (Stanislov Ivano & Craig, 2019). These services helps customer to produce independent services rather to serve by employee. Technology like self check-in or information kiosk at hotel and airport, mobile check in application, vending machine for food and beverage, automatic bio metric finger print scanner at airport, baggage drop counter, ticket machine at railway or theme park etc. however many application are at infancy, their adoption and operation are quite costly. As per the study conducted by TCS over the global industries to use artificial intelligence, Banking& Financial services use 21.8% while travel, transportation and Hospitality use only 3.5% across the 13 major industries (TCS Global trend report, 2020). Further, Travel, Tourism & Hospitality (TTH), robotics is increasingly in use for the service. In the report, study conducted over America, Europe and Asia pacific for TTII industries, major use of AI is in the IT (46%), Sale (32%) and customer services 29% (TCS Global trend report, 2020). It seems that technology in the T&H industry is still underutilized or in initial stage. Although, the application of AI technology will give rise to many benefits in the Tourism and Hospitality industry as discussed in this paper. However, it also posses numerous challenges and complexities, the introduction of AI application, especially in mid-sized and independent hotel is not an easy job. Hospitality and tourism

business has always been a service oriented and human involved sector with risen use of chatbots, virtual reality and other technologies, actual human interaction would be restricted. Moreover, pandemic covid-19 has also made businesses to think and adapt accordingly, which making hoteliers to adopt technology not only for sustainability but also to ensuring the protection and safety of their guest and employees.

LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDY

After presenting this paper in conceptual & view point approach, authors realized that AI is the most advanced and emerging subject, where technical and comprehensive study is required to be conducted to know the various technicalities related with topic and to asses & analyze the overall implications of the technology over the tourism and hospitality industry, consumers and the business a further study is need to be conducted for the Indian scenario.

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